

Estimating the external parallax error by deconvolution

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Introduction

The trigonometric parallaxes, typically not very much greater in size than the accidental errors, probably offer the best opportunity to check the external errors of the Hipparcos data. Indirectly, this is not only a check on the parallaxes, but on the positions and proper motions as well. Given the way the observations are put together into the five astrometric parameters, it is difficult to imagine that the positions or proper motions of a set of stars can be seriously wrong, if the parallaxes are shown to be essentially correct. Similarly it is reasonable to assume that if the formal errors of the parallaxes are found to be systematically wrong by a certain factor, then the same factor will apply to the formal errors of the other parameters. Consequently it is of the greatest interest to be able to estimate the average *external* standard error for any given set of Hipparcos parallaxes.

Previously I have attempted to estimate the external parallax errors by comparing with a theoretical distribution of the error-free parallaxes. This could either be derived from a model of the space distribution of the stars, or it could be some *ad hoc* analytical function with a few adjustable parameters. The external error was found by adjusting the various parameters of the probability densities of the parallaxes and of the observation errors until a convolution of the two functions agreed as well as possible with the observed density. The first method gave some useful results with the 'provisional data' (A&A 258, 134, 1992), but apparently fails with the much more accurate data now available. While this result by itself is very interesting it makes this particular method fairly useless for the present purpose. In later experiments I preferred the more flexible 'beta' model (NDAC/LO/142, 13 July 1992) originally conceived as a generalization of the cut-off power law proposed by R. Hanson (MNRAS 192, 347, 1980).

However, as the accuracy of the data is improved and we are motivated to study many different stellar samples selected, e.g., according to magnitude and colour, it soon becomes evident that any pre-defined parametric representation is doomed to fail at least in some particular case. In fact the only constraint that can be introduced with complete confidence is the non-negativity condition, i.e., that true parallaxes cannot be negative. For greater generality we are thus induced to investigate non-parametric estimation methods which do not depend on any pre-conceived model distribution. In practice such methods amount to some kind of deconvolution of the observed distribution.

Apparently, attempts to deduce the true parallax distribution by deconvolution were made almost as soon as a sufficient number of parallax determinations had been compiled. The first (?) such result is published in the *Greenwich Observations of Stellar Parallax 1913-1924* (1925), where it is noted (p. viii) that 'As no stars have been omitted on account of negative parallaxes, the actual distribution of the stars according to the size of their parallaxes gives a good idea of the true probable error.' A formula by A.S. Eddington (MNRAS 73, 359, 1913) was applied (p. x) to the smoothed observed distribution in order to derive the true distribution; not surprisingly, this gave negative frequencies for a part of the curve. The derived true distribution was therefore modified to conform with the hypothesis of no negative parallaxes, and convolved with the assumed error function. This was found to agree well with

the observed frequencies. Thus it was shown that the true errors could not be much greater than the formal errors. In this case the main purpose of the exercise was clearly to investigate the external errors. Later writers on the subject of parallax distributions (e.g., F. Dyson, MNRAS 86, 686, 1926) were perhaps more interested in the systematic statistical corrections to be applied to the parallaxes, or specifically: how to turn negative values into positive ones. Using another result attributed to Eddington, Dyson derived the mean correction as a function of the observed value and the apparent distribution; the ‘true’ distribution could then be obtained by regrouping the corrected values. Interestingly, the same method was recently derived in the context of bayesian estimation by F. Arenou (thesis, Observatoire de Paris, 1993) in his study of the errors of preliminary Hipparcos parallaxes.

A slightly different approach was taken by E. Holmberg (Medd. Lund Ser. II, 97, 1938). In effect he uses Eddington’s formula to compute the mean correction as a function of the observed parallax, but he also obtains the higher moments of the correction. He notes (p. 56) that ‘The distribution of the individual corrections [...] is nothing but the distribution of the true parallax values that correspond to the observed value in question. Thus, the true distribution of all parallaxes can be obtained by summing up all these elementary distributions.’ This comes very close in spirit to the bayesian method.

Although these methods may produce ‘true’ distributions with (almost) no negative values, they do not explicitly incorporate the non-negativity condition. In the next section I will show how this condition is very naturally included in an iterative estimation method which is in fact equivalent to the well-known Richardson-Lucy deconvolution.

The proposed method can be summarized as follows. First the observed distribution is deconvolved according to some assumed error law while imposing the non-negativity condition for the resulting (error-free) distribution. The resulting distribution is then convolved with the same error law and compared with the observed distribution. The process is repeated with different error distributions until the best fit is achieved. For arbitrary distributions this process would have been circular, but that is in fact avoided here thanks to the non-negativity condition. In practice it is only the tail of negative observed parallaxes that determines the error law.

Again I want to emphasize that the purpose of this exercise is not to determine the true parallax distribution (which may be extremely difficult), but to estimate the errors. The true distribution enters however as a necessary intermediate step.

Bayesian deconvolution

Let p denote the observed parallax for a particular star and ϖ the true parallax. In a probabilistic approach these values are regarded as realizations of the continuous random variables P, Π characterized by the joint probability density function (pdf) $f_{P,\Pi}(p, \varpi)$. The observed frequency of parallaxes corresponds to the marginal pdf

$$f_P(p) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_{P,\Pi}(p, \varpi) d\varpi, \quad (1)$$

while the purpose of the deconvolution is to estimate the unconditional distribution of ϖ , i.e., the marginal pdf

$$f_\Pi(\varpi) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_{P,\Pi}(p, \varpi) dp. \quad (2)$$

Introducing the conditional densities $f_{P|\Pi=\varpi}$ and $f_{\Pi|P=p}$ we can write

$$f_{P,\Pi}(p, \varpi) = f_\Pi(\varpi) f_{P|\Pi=\varpi}(p) \quad (3a)$$

$$= f_P(p) f_{\Pi|P=p}(\varpi). \quad (3b)$$

Subsequently we shall assume that the conditional density of p is a function of $p - \varpi$ only (i.e., not of p and ϖ separately), and write

$$f_{P|\Pi=\varpi}(p) = g(p - \varpi) \quad (4)$$

where $g(x)$ is the pdf of the observation error $x = p - \varpi$. Typically g may be a centred gaussian pdf of given standard deviation σ , but the formulation below is valid for any reasonable error law.

From Eqs (1), (3a) and (4) we obtain the convolution integral

$$f_P(p) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_{\Pi}(\varpi) g(p - \varpi) d\varpi, \quad (5)$$

which together with (3b) gives

$$f_{\Pi|P=p}(\varpi) = \frac{f_{\Pi}(\varpi) g(p - \varpi)}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_{\Pi}(\varpi') g(p - \varpi') d\varpi'}. \quad (6)$$

This is Bayes' formula for the conditional distribution of ϖ , given the observed value p , the prior density of true parallaxes f_{Π} , and the error law g . Referring to f_{Π} as the prior density may be a bit misleading here, since we shall try to *estimate* f_{Π} , which then does not represent any *a priori* assumption about the state of nature.

Now consider a sample of stars ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) for which we can assume that the given density functions f_{Π} and g apply. Then each observed value p_i provides a posterior density for ϖ_i according to Eq. (6). Taking the average of the n posterior densities results in the pdf

$$h(\varpi) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_{\Pi}(\varpi) g(p_i - \varpi)}{\int f_{\Pi}(\varpi') g(p_i - \varpi') d\varpi'}. \quad (7)$$

Let us now calculate the expectation of this function, assuming that the p_i 's follow the pdf f_P . For the arbitrary function $\phi(p)$ we have $E[\phi(p)] = \int \phi(p) f_P(p) dp$. Applied to Eq. (7) this gives

$$\begin{aligned} E[h(\varpi)] &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{f_{\Pi}(\varpi) g(p - \varpi)}{\int f_{\Pi}(\varpi') g(p - \varpi') d\varpi'} f_P(p) dp \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_{P,\Pi}(p, \varpi) dp \\ &= f_{\Pi}(\varpi). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Loosely speaking, h converges to f_{Π} as $n \rightarrow \infty$, provided of course that the correct functions f_{Π} and g are used to calculate h .

The practical usefulness of this result depends on the circumstance that h may be a reasonable estimate of the actual density of true parallaxes even if the prior density f_{Π} used in Eq. (7) deviates from it. This immediately leads to an iterative procedure for estimating f_{Π} , starting from some (almost) arbitrary initial density, calculating h and using this h as an improved approximation of f_{Π} for the next iteration, etc. With $h_k(\varpi)$ denoting the k th approximation of f_{Π} the iteration formula can be summarily written

$$h_{k+1}(\varpi) = h_k(\varpi) \times \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{g(p_i - \varpi)}{\int h_k(\varpi') g(p_i - \varpi') d\varpi'} \quad (k = 0, 1, \dots). \quad (9)$$

If the initial density satisfies the non-negativity condition [$h_0(\varpi) = 0$ for $\varpi < 0$], then all subsequent approximations will clearly satisfy the same condition. In fact, a useful initial density is simply

$$h_0(\varpi) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \varpi \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

It does not matter that this is not a proper (finite) pdf; the normalization integral in Eq. (9) ensures that the next and following approximations are proper density functions.

Equation (9) is equivalent to the so-called Richardson-Lucy iteration pioneered in the early seventies by W.H. Richardson (JOSA 62, 55, 1972) and L.B. Lucy (AJ 79, 745, 1974). Probably because of its relatively strong computational demands, at least in two-dimensional applications, it has only recently enjoyed some popularity mainly as an alternative to Maximum Entropy methods. For the present application its main advantages seem to be the simple and natural way to include the non-negativity condition, the sound theoretical basis, and the circumstance that it does not depend on any (half-arbitrary) ‘smoothing’ parameter balancing the smoothness of the solution against the truthful reproduction of the observations. There are nevertheless problems with the method, to which I return in the final section.

An example

Figure 1 is an example of the application of the proposed method. The histogram shows the distribution of 5700 parallaxes in the NDAC 18 months solution with $9.1 < H_p < 12.6$ and $2.05 < \sigma_{\text{int}} < 2.40$, where σ_{int} is the internal (formal) standard error obtained in the sphere solution. The thin solid curve is the estimate of the true parallax pdf $h(\varpi)$ obtained after 20 Richardson-Lucy iterations, assuming a gaussian error distribution with standard deviation $\sigma_{\text{ext}} = 2.30$. The thick curve was obtained by convolving the estimated true parallax pdf with the assumed error function.

In this example the agreement between the thick curve and the histogram is on the whole fairly good. In fact the value $\sigma_{\text{ext}} = 2.30$ was selected to minimize the overall chi-square difference between the two distributions ($\chi^2 = 1251$ with 1320 d.o.f.). On closer inspection one gets the impression that the negative tail of the histogram falls off somewhat steeper than the thick curve for moderately small parallaxes (2–3 mas), while there seem to be too many observed points below –3 mas. The deviations are more readily seen in Figure 2, which is a plot of the ranked predicted values against the ranked observed values.* This type of behaviour, which occurs in many of the investigated samples, seems to indicate a positive kurtosis of the actual error pdf. This in turn could possibly be ‘explained’ in terms of a mixture of gaussians with different standard widths. Nevertheless it appears that the σ_{ext} obtained by this method is a fair approximation of the true rms error.

* The predicted value of the i th smallest parallax is computed as $F^{-1}[i/(n+1)]$, where n is the total number of data points and F is the predicted distribution (*i.e.*, the integral of the thick curve in Figure 1).

Figure 1. The distribution of 5700 observed parallaxes (histogram), the estimated true distribution h obtained by deconvolution (thin curve), and the convolution of h with the assumed error function (thick curve).

Figure 2. The negative tail of Figure 1 plotted in a different way to bring out more clearly the difference between the observed data and the fitted function. The abscissa is the ranked observed parallax, the ordinate is the estimated ranked value based on the fitted distribution.

A comparison of internal and external errors

The NDAC 18 months sphere solution gives accepted single-star parameters for 90,756 stars in common with the FAST non-iterated solution. I have studied the external errors of the NDAC parallaxes for this sample with a view to determine if the variance estimates (described in NDAC/LO/144) are reasonable. In particular, it is interesting to see how the external errors relate to the internal (formal) errors as a function of magnitude. The material was divided into 16 subgroups of about the same size (some 5700 stars) by taking first the quartiles in H_p , and then divide each such magnitude group into four quartiles according to σ_{int} . The σ_{ext} was estimated for each subgroup as described above. However, the χ^2 minimization was only done on the negative part of the histogram, because this was generally found to be more sensitive to variations in σ_{ext} . The table below gives the mean magnitude, mean internal error, estimated external error, and the ratio of external to internal errors for each subgroup.

$\langle H_p \rangle$	$\langle \sigma_{\text{int}} \rangle$	σ_{ext}	$\sigma_{\text{ext}} / \langle \sigma_{\text{int}} \rangle$
6.607	1.158	1.319	1.139
6.680	1.491	1.648	1.105
6.812	1.750	1.878	1.073
7.036	2.087	2.416	1.158
8.096	1.698	1.725	1.016
8.097	1.322	1.277	0.966
8.125	1.951	1.875	0.961
8.178	2.299	2.271	0.988
8.768	1.905	1.849	0.971
8.776	1.480	1.415	0.956
8.802	2.171	2.276	1.048
8.838	2.582	2.587	1.002
9.519	1.738	1.697	0.976
9.549	2.241	2.297	1.025
9.707	2.561	2.687	1.049
10.104	3.125	3.392	1.085
Mean value			1.032
Standard deviation			0.063

A plot of σ_{ext} versus σ_{int} (Figure 3) shows a remarkably good agreement on the whole. This is apparent also from the ratio in the last column of the table. However, plotting the ratio versus magnitude (Figure 4) reveals a systematic difference in the sense that the internal errors are underestimated for the bright stars by some 10–15%.

Figure 3. Estimated external standard error plotted against the mean internal (formal) error for 16 samples of observed parallaxes.

Figure 4. The ratio of external/internal standard error plotted against magnitude.

A problem of convergence

The results described above were always obtained after 20 Richardson-Lucy iterations. This number was chosen because it appeared, in the few cases when many more iterations were tried, that little happened with the estimated σ_{ext} after the first 10 to 20 iterations. Also the goodness-of-fit did not generally improve much after that; in fact in some cases very slow, low-amplitude oscillations could be observed in the χ^2 versus the iteration number, so that a stopping rule based on that statistic could not easily be defined. Thus it would seem that we have in practice a converged solution after relatively few iterations.

However, if we look at the estimated ‘true’ distribution $h_k(\varpi)$ versus iteration number (k), we get a distinctly different picture (Figure 5). In fact there is no sign of convergence in $h_k(\varpi)$ even after 200 iterations—each doubling of k seems to bring approximately the same change in $h_k(\varpi)$. The resulting distribution also seems to be increasingly erratic with more iterations. On the other hand, after convolution with the assumed gaussian the curves converge nicely to the best fit of the observed pdf (Figure 6). It is quite illuminating (and surprising) to see how the large and increasing wobbles in Figure 5 are almost completely taken out by the convolution in Figure 6. Obviously these wobbles represent a near-singularity of the integral equation (5), and the iterations seem to amplify this component of the solution.

From a purely pragmatic viewpoint, since we are really not interested in the ‘true’ distribution, we could say that the present method works very fine: it gives a consistent and well-converged solution for the external error. However, from a more philosophical viewpoint the lack of convergence in $h_k(\varpi)$ is quite unsatisfactory, for it means that we really do not get the bayesian estimate of the true distribution, but something else. Thus the claim for a sound theoretical basis is in fact quite hollow.

Figure 5. Estimates of the 'true' parallax distribution for the same sample as in Figure 1, as obtained after 1, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100 and 200 Richardson-Lucy iterations.

Figure 6. The curves in Figure 5 after convolution with the assumed error function (a gaussian with standard deviation 2.3 mas).